

Variation in Mesomorphic Characteristics with an Alteration in Molecular Structure : 4-(4'-n-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)benzylidene-4''-chloroanilines and -4-(4'-n-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)benzylidene-3''-chloroanilines

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Mesomorphism has been exhibited by compounds of several homologous series¹. Mesomorphism is generally attributed to the molecular geometry and the molecular forces arising therefrom. Our earlier reported work²⁻⁵ has been on several homologous series with $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{COO}-$ and $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$ central linkages and CH_3 , OCH_3 , H , NO_2 and Cl as the terminal groups. Here we report two homologous series with $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{COO}-$ and $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$ as central linkages and Cl as terminal group in *para* (series I) and in *meta* (series II) positions. The study was undertaken with the view to find the variation in mesomorphic characteristics with the changed position of the terminal chloro group.

Results and Discussion

All the homologues of the homologous series 4-(4'-n-alkoxybenzoyloxy)benzylidene-4''-chloroanilines (I) are mesogens (Fig. 1); however, the first four compounds decompose before passing into the isotropic phase at high temperatures. No indication of alternating odd-even effect is observed for the N-1 transition curve. The slope of the N-1 transition curve indicates that it is high melting series. The first member of the series has the range of phase of approximately 145° while the last one has of 135° , indicating thereby only a 10° narrowing of the phase as the series is ascended. Polymesomorphism

begins from the C_4 member with the appearance of smectic phase and continues upto C_{10} member; the C_{12} and onward members show only smectic phase. The S-N curve rises very steeply

Fig. 1. 4-(4'-n-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)benzylidene-4''-chloroanilines : (x) decomposition, (●) solid mesomorphic/solid isotropic, (○) nematic-isotropic, (Δ) smectic-nematic and (x) smectic-isotropic.

observing a maximum at the C₈ homologue, after which the curve falls upto the C₁₀ member. The S-I curve is in continuity with the N-I curve unlike the S-N curve. It is observed that in the first three members the nematic phase has threaded texture, whereas it is homeotropic in the rest of the members, however the smectic phase has focal conic fan shaped S_A texture.

The homologous series 4-(4'-n-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzylidene-3'-chloroanilines (**II**) is also a high melting series (Fig. 2). The first two members

Fig. 2. 4-(4'-n-Alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzylidene-3'-chloroanilines : (x) decomposition, (●) solid mesomorphic/solid isotropic, (o) nematic-isotropic, (Δ) smectic-nematic and (x) smectic-isotropic.

are nematogens. Polymesomorphism is exhibited between C₃ (monotropic-smectic) and C₈ homologues; C₁₀ and onward members are purely smectogens. No odd-even effect in the N-I transitions is observed in this series too. The N-I transition curve shows falling tendency as the series is ascended; the S-I curve shows continuity with the N-I curve. The S-N curve shows rising tendency as the series ascends; it seems to merge with the N-I curve beyond the C₈ homologue. The texture of the nematic

and smectic mesophases are identical to those of series **I** members. The series is more smectogenic than nematogenic.

Series	R ₁	R ₃
I ,	H	Cl
II ,	Cl	H
III ,	H	H
IV ,	H	CH ₃
V ,	H	OCH ₃

Examination of the above two series for comparison shows that the series **I** has the higher overall transitions than those of series **II**. In series **I**, the smectic phase is induced at the C₄ homologue and continues to be exhibited together with nematic phase upto C₁₀ homologue, whereas in series **II**, the smectic phase is induced at C₃ homologue and continues to be exhibited together with nematic phase upto C₈ homologue. For both the series, in higher homologues, smectic phase is the only phase present. The molecular geometry of the two series is comparable. The breadth of the molecules is increased with Cl group occupying the 3-position in series **II**, thereby increasing the lateral attractions sufficiently causing them to be more smectogenic than series **I**. The first four members of series **I** decompose at high transitions, whereas no decomposition is observed in series **II** (Tables 1 and 2). Both the series, however, show identical textures of the nematic and smectic phases.

Table 3 shows the average thermal stabilities and the stage of commencement of the smectic phase for the following homologous series, selected for comparative study. Most of the molecular geometry of all the homologous series under comparison is common; the only uncommon part being the different terminal groups at one end in them. The reason for variations observed in the average thermal stabilities and the commencement of the smectic phase be looked upon due to different terminal

groups of these series and the molecular forces arising therefrom. The lower N-1 thermal stability in series **II** may be due to the less terminal attractions. The higher N-1 thermal stabilities in series **I**, **IV** and **V** may be due to the overall greater polarisability of the molecules with Cl, CH₃ and OCH₃ terminal groups respectively. The higher values of S-N or S-1 thermal stability in series **I** is due to the tilting effect of C-Cl dipole⁶ and the lower thermal stability may be due to the lower lateral attractions in series **III**, **IV** and **V**. The N-1 and S-N thermal stabilities of series **II** are lower than those of series **I**. This can be due to the lower overall polarisability of molecules in the former series.

The study suggests the following orders for N-1 and S-N or S-1 average thermal stability for the various terminal substituents: OCH₃ > Cl > CH₃ > H (nematic order), and Cl > CH₃ > H > OCH₃ (smectic order). The order is in good agreement with that reported by Gray⁷.

TABLE 1-4-(4'-n-ALKOXYCINNAMOYLOXY)-
BENZYLIDENE-4-CHLOROANILINES (I)

n-Alkyl group	Transition temp (°C)		
	Smectic	Nematic	Isotropic
Methyl	-	156.0	300 ^a
Ethyl	-	155.5	294 ^a
Propyl	-	141.0	287 ^a
Butyl	140.5	174.5	281 ^a
Pentyl	128.5	205.0	280.0
Hexyl	120.0	222.0	272.5
Heptyl	125.0	232.0	268.0
Octyl	120.0	236.5	257.5
Decyl	111.5	232.5	252.0
Dodecyl	114.5	-	240.0
Hexadecyl	116.0	-	232.5
Octadecyl	91.0	-	224.0

^aDecomposition point

Experimental

The following homologues were prepared by the reported methods: (i) 4-n-alkoxybenzaldehydes⁸, (ii) *trans*-4-n-alkoxycinnamic acids⁹, (iii) *trans*-4-n-alkoxycinnamoyl chlorides² and (iv) 4-(4'-n-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzaldehydes².

TABLE 2-4-(4'-n-ALKOXYCINNAMOYLOXY)BENZYLIDENE-
3''-CHLOROANILINES (II)

n-Alkyl group	Transition temp (°C)		
	Smectic	Nematic	Isotropic
Methyl	-	142.0	184.0
Ethyl	-	128.0	178.0
Propyl	(119.0) ^a	126.5	168.5
Butyl	113.5	136.5	169.0
Pentyl	103.0	143.5	166.0
Hexyl	99.0	148.5	162.5
Heptyl	92.5	151.5	158.5
Octyl	79.5	154.5	155.5
Decyl	56.5	-	147.5
Dodecyl	64.0	-	140.0
Tetradecyl	73.0	-	131.0
Hexadecyl	77.5	-	120.0
Octadecyl	77.0	-	109.5

^aIndicates monotropy

TABLE 3-AVERAGE THERMAL STABILITIES (°C)

Series	I	II	III ^a	IV ^b	V ^a
N-1	266.0 (C ₆ -C ₈)	162.3 (C ₅ -C ₇)	195.0 (C ₆ -C ₈)	248.0 (C ₆ -C ₈)	270.0 (C ₆ -C ₈)
S-N or	232.2	125.1	168.2	190.0	167.2
S-1	(C ₁₂ -C ₁₈)	(C ₁ -C ₁₈)			
Commencement of S _m phase	C ₄	C ₃	C ₆	C ₇	C ₈

^aRef. 1. ^bRef. 2.

The Schiff base esters, namely, 4-(4'-n-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzylidene-4''-chloroanilines (**I**) and 4-(4'-n-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzylidene-3''chloroanilines (**II**) were prepared by condensing equimolar amounts (0.01 mol) of 4-(4'-n-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzaldehydes with 4-chloroaniline and 3-chloroaniline respectively in ethanol (20 ml) containing a few drops of acetic acid and refluxing the mixture for 2-3 h. The products were recrystallised from benzene-ethanol (20 : 80) mixture. The C, H and N elemental analysis (Coleman 33) data for both the homologous series **I** and **II**, confirm with the calculated ones. The transitions and mesomorphic characteristics were studied by using a Kofler hot-stage polarising microscope.

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